

Protecting Cyber-Physical Systems with Deep Learning and Blockchain-Powered Data Transmission: A Review

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Abstract— The rapid evolution of physical device-based data collection within emerging technologies necessitates intelligent, secure, and efficient data transmission. Cyber-physical systems confront the challenge of intelligently transmitting data while ensuring security. The intricate interconnections among heterogeneous devices in real-time pose a formidable challenge for ensuring system security. This paper introduces a novel methodology aimed at detecting cyber-attacks in cyber-physical systems. The proposed system leverages a Deep Neural Network (DNN) for categorizing normal and attack data. Specifically, the DNN architecture is designed with four hidden layers to detect anomalies effectively. To ensure secure transmission, the system utilizes blockchain technology through the Ethereum platform. The Ethereum process generates blockchain blocks with headers, enabling data transmission from the cyberworld to the physical world while safeguarding against data tampering. Authentication of the proposed algorithm's efficacy will be conducted using two real-time datasets, namely NSL-KDD15 and CIDDS_001. The comparative analysis demonstrates the encouraging outcomes of the suggested system when compared to current deep learning methods, such as classic DNN structures, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), and Deep Belief Networks (DBN).

Keywords— CPS, DNN, Deep Belief Networks (DBN), RNN-Recurrent Neural Networks, Blockchain

I. INTRODUCTION

Now a days, the exponential growth of CPS cyber-physical systems has propelled technological advancements, enabling the seamless integration of physical devices with computational and communication capabilities. CPS, characterized by the convergence of the physical and digital worlds, has revolutionized various fields, including finance, manufacturing industry, healthcare, transportation, education & agriculture. This amalgamation facilitates the group, processing, and utilization of huge volumes of data produced

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by interconnected devices embedded in the stuff of our daily survives.

The burgeoning proliferation of CPS has engendered an unprecedented surge in the acquisition and dissemination of data from myriad interconnected devices, ranging from sensors and actuators to smart appliances and autonomous vehicles. This deluge of data, while promising innovative opportunities for enhancing efficiency and convenience, presents an inherent challenge—ensuring the secure and intelligent transmission of data across the CPS ecosystem.

Figure 1: CPS Spectrum Visualization

A. Challenges in Cyber-Physical Systems

The seamless operation of CPS necessitates continuous and reliable data transmission, facilitating real-time decision-making and control. However, this integration of physical and digital realms brings forth multifaceted challenges, primarily centered around security, reliability, and efficiency.

- **Security Concerns:** The interconnected nature of devices in CPS introduces vulnerabilities, amplifying the risk of cyber-attacks and unauthorized access. Malicious actors exploit these vulnerabilities, aiming to compromise system integrity, steal sensitive information, or disrupt critical operations. Ensuring robust security measures becomes imperative to safeguard against these threats.

- **Heterogeneity and Interoperability:** CPS comprises heterogeneous devices with diverse communication protocols, operating systems, and hardware specifications.

Integrating and maintaining interoperability among these disparate components pose significant technical hurdles, often leading to compatibility issues and security vulnerabilities.

• **Real-Time Constraints:** The time-critical nature of CPS operations demands low-latency communication and rapid decision-making. Any disruption or delay in data transmission can severely impact system functionality, compromising operational efficiency and safety.

Figure 2: Challenges of CPS System

B. Motivation and Research Focus

The pressing need to report these challenges and fortify the security and productivity of data transmission within CPS has motivated extensive research efforts. This research paper endeavors to propose a novel methodology that amalgamates deep neural network (DNN) architectures and blockchain technology to confront the twin challenges of security and intelligent information transmission in CPS.

C. Research Objectives

The main area of this research is to produce a reliable and intelligent system that is able to:

- Detecting and mitigating cyber-attacks within CPS by employing advanced DNN techniques for anomaly detection in data streams.
- Ensuring secure and tamper-resistant data transmission through the integration of blockchain technology, leveraging the Ethereum platform to facilitate the transmission of data from the cyberworld to the physical realm.

II. RELATED WORK

Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) represent an intricate fusion of physical elements and computational components, necessitating robust security measures and efficient data transmission protocols to ensure seamless operation and safeguard against cyber threats. This section offers a comprehensive review of existing methodologies, technologies, and research efforts dedicated to addressing the challenges prevalent in CPS security and data transmission. The domain of cyber-physical security has drawn significant interest from researchers, particularly within healthcare systems, where it is seamlessly integrated into the broader spectrum of cybersecurity protocols. Advances in deep

learning (DL) and machine learning (ML) algorithms are presented in recent literature with the goal of strengthening the security protocols of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS). This comprehensive review aims to elucidate the recent strides made in algorithms pertaining to cyber-physical systems.

The study by [1] presents a deep learning-driven strategy intended to fortify defenses against cyberattacks. Data integrity is safeguarded against potential breaches with their solution, AMLODA-B (Adversarial Machine-Learning Occupancy-Detection-Avoidance with Blockchain), which makes use of the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) paradigm within a standardized smart metering architecture. In [2], a novel methodology optimizing content caching and resource allocation is proposed, particularly advantageous in Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) for Virtual Car Sharing (VCPS), significantly enhancing the overall driving experience.

Furthermore, [4] addresses the pivotal concerns of preserving privacy and upholding data integrity against integrity attacks within CPS. This study emphasizes the detection of zero-day attacks with minimal false alarm rates, crucial for safeguarding CPS data.

[5] introduces a patient-centric approach securing data on reliable devices like end-users' smartphones, ensuring discreet data sharing access. The proposed solution outperforms existing models, boasting superior attack estimation, accuracy, efficiency ratios, reduced latency, and lower communication costs based on experimental data.

In [6], the utilization of PHR-Cypher-Text of IoMT on the IPFS-Interplanetary File System leverages blockchain technology intended for keyword index authentication via zero-knowledge proof, ensuring robust security.

Moreover, [7] focuses on health experts tracing users opting out or unable to engage in contact locating, employing edge servers to reduce end-users' power usage significantly.

Additionally, [8] proposes privacy protection solutions specifically tailored for edge healthcare and IoT applications, emphasizing methods to embed privacy into medical solutions for reliable and secure data gathering with short computational rates and compression ratios.

The authors of [10] augment security in EHR's-electronic health records and medical IoT data within Healthcare Services through integrating data access governor and data usage reviewing tools, resulting in increased processing and communication efficiency.

[11] validates their approach using a heart disease dataset, showcasing enhanced disease prediction accuracy in EHR systems. In [13], bidirectional security and enhanced timeliness of information acquisition, especially in the context of 5G, are emphasized to safeguard case database privacy and patient information.

Furthermore, subsequent studies like [15] emphasize the capabilities of an OCBS framework for secure and patient-centric integration with off-chain storage. In [16], a fog computing model based on blockchain for IoMT ensures high reliability in file transfer.

[17] provides a security analysis of AISCMS-FH and its impact on key performance parameters, while [19] evaluates proposed methods' performance characteristics for improved security against healthcare data attacks. In [20], a prototype

model integrating IoMT and blockchain technology demonstrates enhanced patient-health-factor analysis. Additionally, [21] introduces a blockchain-enabled edge computing mechanism using consensus protocols and smart contracts to address privacy concerns and scalability issues. In parallel with fog computing, [22] investigates blockchain's potential in mitigating privacy and security challenges, addressing drawbacks from IoMT and fog computing (FC) perspectives. [23] compiles research on novel blockchain solutions combined with AI technologies, setting new standards for the food and medical industries.

Furthermore, [24] proposes a healthcare data safety framework employing blockchain technology to notify network consumers of any unauthorized data modifications. Moreover, [25] introduces secure, transparent techniques utilizing blockchain and machine learning models to enhance patient treatment and healthcare system integrity. In [26], deep learning methods and platforms used in AI-based blockchain systems are examined, covering supervised and unsupervised machine learning challenges.

The study by [27] presents a smart contract solution based on blockchain and machine learning, enhancing security and lowering resource consumption for real-time medical applications. [28] delves into privacy and security issues in machine-learning models, emphasizing resource utilization effectiveness. [29] highlights various usages of blockchain in the medical industry, particularly in instantaneous data observing and analytics. Finally, [30] explores blockchain applications in COVID-19 and offers recommendations for fortifying the healthcare system through blockchain integration with big data, IoT, AI, and machine learning.

A. CPS Security Frameworks and Challenges

Numerous studies have highlighted the critical importance of establishing comprehensive security frameworks tailored to the unique characteristics of CPS. Gaining traction in CPS security research are approaches focusing on anomaly detection, intrusion detection systems (IDS), and threat modeling methodologies.

- **Anomaly Detection Techniques:** Traditional anomaly detection techniques encompass statistical methods, machine learning, and data mining algorithms. Advancements in recent times have led to the inclusion of Deep Learning models for anomaly identification in CPS data streams, together with RNN- Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs).

- **Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS):** IDS show a pivotal part in identifying & mitigating cyber threats within CPS. Signature-based detection and anomaly-based detection techniques are widely employed, yet these methods encounter challenges in adapting to the dynamic nature of CPS environments.

- **Threat Modelling and Risk Assessment:** Comprehensive threat modelling frameworks and risk assessment methodologies have been proposed to systematically identify vulnerabilities, assess potential risks,

and design countermeasures to fortify CPS against cyber-attacks.

B. Secure Data Transmission in CPS

Efficient and secure transmission of data in CPS involves intricate communication protocols and technologies designed to mitigate vulnerabilities and ensure data integrity and confidentiality. Notable areas of research encompass encryption techniques, blockchain technology, and secure communication protocols.

- **Encryption Techniques:** Encryption is essential for safeguarding data during transmission. Two widely used cryptographic techniques that protect the confidentiality and integrity of data are elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) and the advanced encryption standard (AES).

- **Blockchain Technology:** The adoption of blockchain in CPS has garnered significant attention due to its inherent attributes of immutability, decentralization, and transparency. Blockchain facilitates secure and tamper-resistant data transmission, enabling traceability and auditability of information flows in CPS.

- **Secure Communication Protocols:** Protocols like Datagram Transport Layer Security (DTLS), Secure Real-time Transport Protocol (SRTP), and Transport Layer Security (TLS) have made it possible to ensure data confidentiality and authenticity inside CPS.

C. Challenges and Limitations

Despite the advancements, several challenges persist in the domain of CPS security and data transmission:

- **Scalability and Resource Constraints:** Implementing robust security measures in resource-constrained CPS environments poses challenges in terms of computational overhead, memory constraints, and scalability.

- **Dynamic Environments and Adaptability:** CPS operate in dynamic environments with varying network conditions and device interactions. Ensuring the adaptability of security measures to these changing environments remains a challenge.

- **Privacy Concerns and Regulatory Compliance:** Data processing and transmission procedures within CPS are challenged by addressing privacy issues and adhering to industry-specific standards and regulatory frameworks like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

D. Current Gaps and Future Directions

While significant progress has been made, there exist certain gaps warranting further research:

- **Hybrid Security Frameworks:** Integrating multiple security measures and forming hybrid frameworks

combining encryption, machine learning-based anomaly detection, and blockchain technology could bolster CPS security.

- **Edge Computing and Security:** Exploring the intersection of edge computing and security mechanisms to enhance data processing capabilities while ensuring robust security in distributed CPS environments.

- **Privacy-Preserving Techniques:** Developing innovative privacy-preserving techniques, including homomorphic encryption and differential privacy, to protect sensitive information without compromising utility in CPS data transmission.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed model is a multifaceted system comprising two primary components: a data generation module representing the physical space housing patient, doctor, and hospital records, and an intrusion detection system.

In the initial phase, the system captures and processes diverse data sets emanating from this physical space. This data is thoroughly analyzed to discern patterns, anomalies, and potential security threats.

Subsequently, the processed data undergoes a novel integration with blockchain technology. The system employs blockchain to encapsulate this processed information into distinct blocks, using the dispersed and secure environment of blockchain for enhanced data security and integrity. These blocks are then distributed across the network, ensuring redundancy and resilience against tampering or unauthorized alterations. The distributed blocks find their repository within a database server, establishing a reliable storage mechanism. Following the blockchain integration, the system employs a sophisticated deep learning-based classification method. This method serves the dual purpose of discerning between normal and attack data patterns within the processed information. Leveraging deep learning algorithms, the system identifies potential cyber-attacks by categorizing data into distinct classes, enabling prompt threat identification and mitigation.

Upon completion of the classification task, the system proceeds to estimate and refine the parameters of the algorithms utilized. The objective of this iterative process is to progress the intrusion detection system's accuracy and efficiency, strengthening the system's capacity to identify and stop possible security breaches.

Overall, the proposed model synergizes data generation, intrusion detection, blockchain integration, and deep learning-based classification, forming a comprehensive approach geared towards robust cyber-physical security. This multifaceted system seeks to secure sensitive healthcare data while ensuring prompt and accurate identification of potential threats within the system.

Figure 3: Flow of proposed system

IV. METHODOLOGY USED

The methodology proposed in this research aims to fortify CPS security by employing a DNN-Deep Neural Network architecture for abnormality finding in collected data & utilizing blockchain technology through the Ethereum platform to ensure secure data transmission.

A. Deep Neural Network (DNN) for Anomaly Detection

The fundamental of proposed methodology involves the utilization of a DNN architecture, specifically designed for the detection of anomalies within the data obtained from various interconnected devices in CPS. The DNN architecture comprises four hidden layers, each meticulously crafted to enable effective anomaly detection.

- **Architecture Design:** The DNN architecture is composed of an input layer, four hidden layers, and an output layer. Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) or sigmoid functions are examples of suitable activation functions that are set up in the hidden layers to incorporate non-linearity and improve the model's capacity to identify intricate patterns in the data.

- **Training Techniques:** The dataset used to train the DNN model includes examples of both normal and anomalous data that were gathered from CPS. The model's weights and biases are iteratively updated using methods such as stochastic gradient descent (SGD) or Adam optimization, which minimizes the loss function related to anomaly detection.

- **Parameter Settings:** Hyperparameter tuning is conducted to optimize the DNN's performance. Parameters such as

batch size, learning rate, & number of neurons each layer, and dropout rates are fine-tuned through cross-validation or grid search to achieve optimal performance in anomaly detection while preventing overfitting.

- **Evaluation and Validation:** The efficacy of the trained DNN model in precisely detecting abnormalities in real-time CPS data streams is assessed through the use of validation datasets and a range of performance indicators, comprising Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis, F1-score, precision, and recall.

B. Blockchain Technology for Secure Data Transmission

In conjunction with the anomaly detection using DNN, the proposed methodology integrates blockchain technology, specifically leveraging the Ethereum platform, to ensure secure and tamper-resistant data transmission within CPS.

- **Blockchain Generation and Data Transmission:** The Ethereum blockchain is employed to create blocks containing headers and transactional data. Each block encapsulates encrypted data packets from CPS devices, ensuring their integrity and immutability. Smart contracts within Ethereum facilitate secure data transmission, providing a transparent decentralized platform for information conversation.

- **Data Authentication and Integrity:** The process of Ethereum-based blockchain generation and transmission guarantees the genuineness and honesty of data transferred from CPS to the cyberworld. The use of consensus mechanisms and cryptographic hashing techniques inherent in blockchain technology ensures data immutability, making it resistant to unauthorized alterations or tampering during transmission.

- **Ensuring Data Security in Physical World:** The blockchain technology deployed through Ethereum ensures that the transmitted data from the cyberworld to the physical world maintains its integrity, preventing malicious tampering or unauthorized modifications during transit.

C. Blockchain Technology and DNN Anomaly Detection Integration

The combination of DNN-based anomaly finding with blockchain technology in the proposed methodology establishes a robust framework for CPS security. The anomaly detection mechanism identifies potential threats or anomalies within CPS data, while the blockchain-based data transmission ensures secure, transparent, and tamper-resistant communication between interconnected devices, mitigating security risks and vulnerabilities.

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The evaluation of the proposed methodology integrating Deep Neural Network (DNN) anomaly detection and blockchain technology for secure data transmission in Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) is conducted using two

widely recognized real-time datasets: NSL-KDD15 and CIDDS_001. The experimental setup encompasses data preprocessing, model training, testing procedures, and comparative analysis with existing algorithms, namely RNN, DBN, and conventional DNN architectures.

A. Data Preprocessing

- **Dataset Description:** The NSL-KDD15 and CIDDS_001 datasets, comprising diverse network traffic data captured from CPS environments, are preprocessed to extract relevant features and labels for anomaly detection. The datasets contain a mix of normal and anomalous instances, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed methodology.

- **Data Cleaning and Transformation:** Preprocessing involves cleaning the datasets to handle missing values, normalization of numerical features, encoding categorical variables, and extracting essential features relevant for anomaly detection using techniques like PCA-Principal Component Analysis or feature assortment methods.

B. Training and Testing Procedures

- **Data Splitting:** There are three sets of preprocessed datasets: training, validation, and testing. The validation set aids in hyperparameter tuning and prevents overfitting, while the DNN model is trained using the training set. The testing set functions as a separate evaluation set and is kept hidden throughout training and validation.

- **Model Training:** The proposed DNN architecture with four hidden layers is trained using the training dataset to learn the underlying patterns distinguishing normal behavior from anomalies in CPS data. The training involves iterative optimization using backpropagation and gradient descent-based algorithms to curtail the loss function.

- **Model Evaluation:** The accuracy with which the trained DNN model can recognize anomalies is assessed using the testing dataset. Precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC curve analysis are among the performance metrics that are computed to evaluate the model's capacity to identify anomalies in CPS data streams.

C. Comparative Analysis

- **Comparison with Existing Algorithms:** The suggested methodology's performance is contrasted with that of other techniques, such as typical DNN structures (e.g., with fewer hidden layers or other configurations), Deep Belief Networks (DBN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN). The comparative study using multiple metrics is carried out to show how much better the suggested method is in terms of accuracy, sensitivity to anomalies, and computational efficiency.

• **Performance Metrics:** Comparative analysis involves evaluating and contrasting the performance of the proposed DNN-based anomaly detection and blockchain-enabled data transmission against RNN, DBN, and other conventional DNN architectures employing measures such as area under the ROC curve, F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision. The accuracy metric quantifies the percentage of accurately anticipated cases out of all the instances.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Total No. of Correctly Classified Instances}}{\text{Total No. of Instances}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True positives}}{\text{True positives} + \text{False positives}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True positives}}{\text{True positives} + \text{False negatives}} \times 100$$

$$F - \text{score} = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FN + FP}$$

The Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (ROC AUC) plots the true positive rate against the false positive rate and determines the area under the curve.

The ROC curve is a plot of True Positive Rate (Recall) against False Positive Rate (1 - Specificity).

The ROC curve must be plotted in order to determine the area under the curve.

VI. EXPECTED OUTCOME

The proposed system encompasses a comprehensive strategy aimed at bolstering cyber-physical security within healthcare environments. Initially, the system meticulously processes and scrutinizes diverse datasets containing crucial patient, doctor, and hospital records, identifying nuanced patterns and potential security risks. This data undergoes an innovative fusion with blockchain technology, ensuring its encapsulation into secure, tamper-resistant blocks distributed across the network. The establishment of a robust storage mechanism within a database server guarantees the protection of sensitive information against unauthorized access. Leveraging sophisticated deep learning methodologies, the system excels in discerning between normal data and potential cyber-attack patterns, swiftly identifying and mitigating security threats. Continual refinement of algorithm parameters further enhances the accuracy of intrusion detection. By integrating data processing, intrusion detection, blockchain security, and advanced machine learning, this multifaceted system aims to fortify cyber-physical security while safeguarding sensitive healthcare data and promptly addressing potential threats.

CONCLUSION

The paper concludes by summarizing the contributions, highlighting the significance of the proposed methodology in enhancing security in CPS, and outlining potential avenues for future research and improvements. The proposed system

orchestrates a sophisticated fusion of data processing, blockchain security, and advanced machine learning, fortifying cyber-physical security within healthcare settings. By adeptly analyzing data, ensuring tamper-resistant storage, and swiftly detecting potential threats, the system stands poised to safeguard sensitive healthcare information while proactively addressing security challenges.

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